

Invisible Machinery in Function, Not Form: User Expectations of Domestic Use Humanoid Robots

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Abstract

This study examines people's expectations about humanoid robots in terms of existing beliefs, opinions and responses to video stimulus of human-robot interactions. A robot intended for home use triggers many feelings in people including fascination, unease, fear and curiosity. A humanoid robot – one designed with humanlike morphology, behaviours, speech or other anthropomorphic indicators – brings additional issues to the human-robot interaction (HRI) scenario. In order to get a full idea of participants' opinions and reactions, we applied post-video viewing questionnaires, physiological measures to test for arousal level and post-video semi-structured interviews to nineteen participants. We expected users to be interested in the robots but also to bring distinct culturally embedded expectations about robots in general. Users described their concerns about robot ownership and interaction, demonstrating emerging patterns of common issues.

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Humanoid robots have varying degrees of anthropomorphic (humanlike) appearance, behaviors and autonomy. Contemporary robotics researchers develop sophisticated humanoid robots that possess abilities ranging from menial domestic tasks to offering sociable companionship through conversation, and are designed to work for and collaborate with human users in a variety of work and home settings. A thorough overview of socially interactive robots was written by Fong, Nourbakhsh and Dautenhahn (2003). There are a growing number of applications for humanoid robots that people can engage as capable creatures or as partners rather than tools, yet research is still early about how to best design robots that interact with people in this way.

People react to humanoid robots with a mix of emotions that can include delight, inquisitiveness and repugnance (Mori, 1970; McDorman, 2005). These reactions depend on many elements, including the type and context of interaction, the robot's appearance and the person's previous exposure to, or expectations of, robots. A person's expectations about robots create mental models that may be bootstrapped for positive experiences of interaction and design impact, regardless of previous values and beliefs that may have roots in cultural influence. The purpose of the present research is to study how people respond to different types of humanoid robots when the robots are situated in a companion context.

In this paper we look at our study results from an interdisciplinary perspective, drawing from cognitive science, industrial design and human factors. One outcome of this research is that it is important to view the issues from the robot's holistic design perspective (function and form) as well as that of human needs (expectations). This paper provides results for building a theoretical framework with which to further understand and develop effective humanoid robot design.

To determine participants' physiological responses to humanoid robots, we recorded participants' skin conductance (SC) while they watched two videos of human-robot interaction. The SC gives us a measure of participants' level of arousal while watching the videos. Our research question related to physiological arousal was: Will robot type (humanlike or machinelike) affect level of arousal?

Previous studies (Dautenhahn, Woods, Kouri, Walters, Koay and Werry, 2005) have used questionnaires to investigate user attitudes towards domestic robots. This study incorporated a questionnaire to examine people's perceptions of a robot's overall appearance and behaviours after viewing videos of each robot.

Participants were also de-briefed about their opinions through a semi-structured interview process and their reactions were recorded through observation and interview notes. Field notes from the interview portions of these sessions were analyzed using qualitative data analysis techniques (Boyatzis, 1998; Ryan and Bernard, 2003).

Method

Nineteen participants completed the study; all were University of Washington students. The mean participant age was 22.8 years ($SD = 4.9$); 53% were women ($n=10$) and 47% were men ($n=9$). Two video clips of separate robots were the stimulus for discussion; each robot (Repliee and Robovie) was contextually introduced as “designed to be a friend or member of the family, offering assistance through social interaction.” Participants first viewed the Repliee and the Robovie videos, shown in random order. Skin conductance measures were recorded continuously as participants watched each video. After watching the videos, participants completed a Likert-scale survey with three questions about their perception of each robot as appearing machine- to human-like, friendly/unfriendly and the comfort level of having that robot in their homes. Participants completed the same questionnaire for each video. They next completed a short demographics survey.

After the last questionnaire was completed, each participant gave a one-on-one semi-structured interview, which was recorded through observation and field notes. Two people manually coded the entire data set using Thematic Analysis and an inductive approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Here, a theme captures something important about the data and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set. The key themes described here (a) characterize a prevalent response from participants and (b) demonstrate something important in relation to the overall research questions used for the physiological investigation. Prevalence was represented in terms of the number of different speakers who articulated the theme across the entire data set.

Materials

The skin conductance measure was recorded continuously using the Infiniti Skin Conductance Flex/Pro Sensor (SA9309M).

The questionnaire asked about humanlikeness vs. machinelikeness, friendliness and comfort level about having the robot in the home.

Two video clips were used as stimuli for discussion. Each of the two videos fit the following criteria:

- Time was approximately three minutes long
- Presented only one robot per video
- Featured robot was humanoid
- Demonstrated a human-robot language interaction (in English)
- Showed the robot's entire body at least once in the video

The robots used in the videos were, as shown in Figures 1 (Repliee Q2, Osaka University and Kokoro Co., Ltd.) and 2 (Robovie, ATR) below.

Fig. 1: Repliee

Fig. 2: Robovie

Each robot differed in its degree of humanlikeness and interactive capabilities. Here, we briefly describe the interactions shown in the videos:

- Repliee Q2 (Ishiguro, Asada, Shapiro, Thielscher, Breazeal, Mataric, and Ishida, 2006) is very humanlike in appearance, voice and through its display of humanlike unconscious behaviours such as looking to the side in conversation. Repliee is covered in a human skin-like exoskeleton and is clothed conservatively and professionally; it speaks English with a Japanese accent. This robot's hands appear very humanlike, but lack individual finger articulation; the robot is seen sitting or standing only, although it demonstrates upper body, head and arm movement. In this video, Repliee's interaction style was humanlike, observing normal rules for conversational turn-taking with the human actors. In the first interaction, Repliee Q2 stands behind an office desk and acts like a receptionist, greeting an adult male and directing him with comments and gestures to an off-screen office. In the other two interactions, it acts as a reporter and conducts

short interviews with human guests.

- Robovie (Kanda, Ishiguro, Imai, and Ono, 2004) is clearly mechanical with a metal exoskeleton, visible power source and wheeled base. This robot's humanoid design is conveyed through its camera eyes, two arms, fluid movement and childlike voice with an American accent. Robovie's behaviour is markedly childlike, requesting hugs, touching and remarking "I love you" to the human actor in the video. In this video, Robovie interacts with an adult male conversationally, introducing itself, commenting on the weather, and asking to play games.

Findings

A one-way repeated measures General Linear Model analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was conducted to determine the differences between participant (n=19) responses to three questions in the post-video questionnaire. Each question was analyzed as a within-subjects factor (response to Robovie vs. response to Repliee). A significant difference was found between participant responses to the human- and machinelikeness question $F(1,18) = 110.250, p < .05$. No significant difference was found for questions regarding friendliness or practicality.

To examine the effects of humanlikeness versus machinelikeness robots on skin conductance measures over time, we again used a repeated measures ANOVA. Results revealed no significant differences between the robots over time.

Themes identified in the interviews showed that the idea of humanoid robots in the home may:

- Arouse unsettling feelings
- Pose a feeling of risk for ownership or association
- Elicit humanlike comparisons
- Connect -robot use with menial tasks
- Stimulate strong emotional reaction and trigger design preferences

In each section below, we include representative comments from participants to illustrate user expectations and general attitudes about domestic humanoid robots.

Invisible Machinery: Robots Arouse Unsettling Feelings

Here, our term *invisible machinery* refers to robots that, through humanlike external design and behaviour, elicit a sense in the user that the object is natural or living. Many participants in this study frequently identified feeling surprise and unease after viewing the robot videos, usually citing robot traits perceived as too humanlike for comfort.

Although Repliee's highly humanlike appearance frequently elicited comments in this vein, Robovie's behaviour also was a source of discomfort for some. The terms "creepy" and "weird" were used repeatedly by participants to describe their emotions after seeing the videos.

"Just the fact that she looks human, but isn't quite human—it's a little bit off...She's just like, she's a little bit slow. She's kind of scary. It's just kind of a gut feeling." (Repliee)

"At first I thought it was a human trying to act like a robot, but then it wasn't. I'm not really sure if I like that or not...It's the idea of whether it's tricking me or not. I feel like it may be trying to trick me." (Repliee)

"There's something just generally creepy about it. There's a mismatch. You have something that looks human, but when it starts moving and starts talking there's that disconnect that's not right. There's that sense of something that doesn't just fit." (Repliee)

"It just doesn't look like a human. It's nothing like a human; that's why it would be a bad robot. I'd prefer that it look like a human, not completely. If it looks too much like a human, it would scare people. Sort of like cartoons—they don't look like actual humans, but they don't look like this robot either." (Robovie)

Terminator Effect: Robots Are Risky Machines

Not surprisingly, popular culture portrayals of dangerous or threatening entities emerged as a touchstone reference among participants about expectations of robot behaviour. Several participants said their mental models of robots were based on what they had seen in a movie or read about in a comic or book. While many participants acknowledged that their fears were based on fictional representations, they persisted with notions that robots were machines that could possibly attain complete autonomy and harm humans, especially in the home. In one case, the robot's demonstrated behaviour in the video activated a clear risk association based on a

Science Fiction reference; Robovie's verbal repetition of phrases was perceived as a sign of potential error that could lead to material or human harm.

"I didn't like the repetition part. Like in science fiction, a robot would start repeating things and then explode." (Robovie)

"You see movies...I don't know...it's probably silly. Like, robots who look like humans, it ends up in a bad way. They attack you. I don't think it's real they could attack you, but it's based on what I've seen in the movies. It's not fact, but it's based on a fear." (Repliee)

"Since it is a robot and it's a machine, there's always a chance for error. You don't know what could happen, like break down...It could break stuff, or it could even possibly harm a person, maybe." (Repliee)

"I think I would have nightmares... It's like every bad science fiction movie. The creature comes alive and appears in the dark. Who knows what it's going to do?" (Repliee)

Frankenstein Effect: Robots Are Humanlike Enough To Stimulate Comparison

Here, we noticed many participants struggled to discuss the robots, searching for ways to verbalize their feelings; although they categorized the robots as machines and identified menial tasks as ideal robot functions, they conceded the robots' appearance or behaviours were humanlike enough that they expected the robots' presence in the home would bring out feelings similar to those of another human in the home. Participants often used language to describe the robots as living or as entities that could be mistaken for living – most frequently by making direct or indirect human comparisons (as opposed to a pet).

"I don't like the idea of this realistic looking robot doing things for me. I probably wouldn't want anybody in my home doing things for me." (Repliee)

"I like living alone and I wouldn't want something with such humanoid qualities to be so present. ...Because I like living alone. I live alone on purpose. I would feel like the purpose is to create the sensation of a human being and I think that cognitively I would understand that wasn't the case, but in practice, it would have some of the similar experience of another presence because it looks more like a person than an appliance." (Repliee)

“I don’t want any kids that are in my home, whether or not they are mine, to really be interacting with someone like that because they might mistake an actual human for a robot like that. They’ll be interacting with a piece of machinery with the idea that it’s someone who’s real.” (Repliee)

“I don’t think I’d want it in my home, period. It’s because, I don’t know, I might come home with it there one day. And I might even mistake it myself as being a real human and then I have to remind myself that it’s just a robot that looks close to what I look like.” (Repliee)

“I like actually that it has kind of humanlike features, but it doesn’t look like it’s trying to be human—which is kind of disarming to me.” (Robovie)

Fantasy Servant: Robots Are For Menial Tasks

In this study we framed the robots as being designed to be a friend or member of the family. However, no participant referred to either robot in this familiar context. In an earlier study (Carpenter, Eliot and Schultheis, 2006), people identified robots as a potential servant in the home. In the present study, this theme again emerged quite clearly. The majority of potential robot tasks identified by participants included organization, heavy lifting, doing the dishes and other household cleaning.

“She’d be useful to be like a secretary or someone who really doesn’t need to do super complex tasks. Just answering the phones, greeting people, guiding them to the right places—it’s easy to have a robot do that.” (Repliee)

“I’d love to have a robot secretary to help me organize my time, or call me when I get a message. We have PDAs, but to have a robot that physically interacts in the environment and interacts with information could be helpful...It could write down phone messages or write a list of things that came up. Just to be able to do the things you do that cross between different systems.” (Robovie)

“At this point, I think robots should be very practical tools. Clean something. Give directions. Help you move something or lift something.” (Robovie)

“Probably end up helping around the house because it’s a robot. Just general cleaning and that type of stuff...Especially at this point, you expect a robot to be subservient and to do what we

tell it to do. You don't expect any indignation. There's no insult to do the vacuuming."

(Robovie)

Looks Matter: Robot Design Impacts User Feelings and Use Scenarios

Finally, many participants stated clear preferences for robot behaviour or appearance.

Movement was a concern; many participants did not want the robot to follow them, nor sit idle for long periods. External design issues centered on the robot's perceived gender, height, dress, voice, sturdiness and whether the robots' abilities matched their appearance.

"I would not want it to follow me. I do not have a dog for a reason [laughs]. The presence of something always there would bother me. If I had a nice robot that was over doing dishes and joined me occasionally, that would be good. I wouldn't want it to always want attention."

(Repliee)

"I don't want it to just not do anything, like just stand there because it would scare me. It's not an actual human. If it'd start moving for a while and then stop moving, it would scare me."

(Repliee)

"I think that, for me, safety regarding a robot would come from not wanting to break it. Not knowing how fragile some part of it is. It's not really a safety issue, but more like a cost issue. Not wanting to interact with it and be the cause of a couple thousand dollars worth of damage."

(Repliee)

"It's weird that physically she'd be more real looking, but the technology doesn't really match with the actual interaction. " (Repliee)

"I was hoping to hear the robot ask different questions because....I don't know. I guess because of its appearance. I expected it to be more humanlike." (Repliee)

"It's just like, you know you're normal typical kind of robot. You can tell that it's a piece of machinery on the outside so you feel more comfortable around it because you know what to expect. I just like the way it looks. Like you kind of already have a schema of what it is from what you know." (Robovie)

“I also think that the size of it was good, too, because it was below your eye level. It’s kind of like a pet dog, closer to the floor, whereas the other robot was at the same equal level. Which really doesn’t make a difference, but subconsciously you’re looking down at something and you think ‘I’m dominant to this.’ So subconsciously, I’m thinking that if a robot is at my same level, I’m expecting more from it or about the equal amount.” (Robovie)

“It’s cute. It looks like what I think a robot should look like. It’s not nearly as human looking as the other one. Obviously, it has characteristics like the eyes and the arms. It’s less threatening because it doesn’t really defy what I think a robot should be.” (Robovie)

“It’s smaller. You wouldn’t mistake it as a human. It seems less threatening. It seems smaller and easier to control. It doesn’t seem as lifelike as the first one.” (Robovie)

“You felt you could control it. Obviously, when I first saw that, I thought ‘robot’; I didn’t think about anything else.” (Robovie)

Discussion

“It would be interesting to see a combination of both of them together. Like if [Repliee] was a little bit shorter and it had the fluid motion that [Robovie] had and the voice it had. The child’s voice, the smaller stature, and the fluidity of movement would make it more real in a way. If it was [Robovie’s] height and had the human characteristics, it would be interesting. I’d find it totally mind boggling to see that. For someone like me, I would like to see that. I’m quite sure for others that would get too close to human characteristics—physical and verbal with some sort of intelligence. It seems like, as I’m saying all this, ‘I like this pen, but I don’t like this about the pen.’ It’s really silly to say this, but it would be interesting to see a more humanoid form. But at the same time, it might not be [interesting] because it’s getting too close to being a human. I think that for me, it would be uncomfortable for a short time. In the long run, if they were common place, we would not have these worries. It’s kind of like a coffeemaker or maybe when the TV was first introduced. People are like, ‘What is this cathode ray tube?’ So it became desensitized and second nature to them. In the long run, it became ‘That’s just an appliance.’ So it might have some purpose, but I don’t have to worry about it replacing my wife and my co-worker and other issues.”

--Interviewee response

The exploratory aspect of this study had some limitations. Video was used as a stimulus for discussion as opposed to actual human-robot interaction; an in-person interaction would be more engaging than watching the videos. The videos showed some of the robots' abilities, but did not completely represent their capabilities in a domestic setting. However, the standardized video interactions allowed for comparison and a focused analysis. Because of the prohibitive cost of access to robots, using video increases the opportunity to examine multiple robots in one study. As shown in other studies (Woods, Walters, Koay, and Dautenhahn, 2006), video can be a helpful tool to gain information about people's expectations of robots.

Many participants cited their expectations about robot abilities, roles, behaviours and appearance as being based on popular culture experience in books and movies, not actual interaction with a real robot. Although the participants acknowledged that such feelings were rooted in fantasy, they also admitted using them as a touchstone for expectations. Robots have a variety of roles in popular culture -- ranging from helpmate to companion to nemesis -- and designers may choose to draw on these models to leverage existing user expectations.

Participants thought Repliee was more humanlike than Robovie, but still expressed unsettling feelings about both. Our findings indicate that people do not respond differently based on physiological measures nor on self-report, given the Invisible Machinery theme.

Design goals to take away from this study rest in finding a balance between user expectations of robots -- such as presenting a somewhat machinelike appearance -- with affordances that clearly indicate the robots' functionality. An overarching concern found in many of the comments regarded the robots' capabilities, and whether the affordances of the designs really indicated a facility to complete certain tasks.

This work represents an early investigation into user expectations about humanoid robots in the home. We hope that these results, while still at a preliminary stage, will encourage discussion on humanoid robot design from a user perspective and may lead to new ways that designers can adapt android systems so people can use them efficiently and with pleasure.

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